

THE USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Jalalova Sevara Janabay kizi

Bachelor degree student Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009220>

Abstract. *This article highlights the use of modern innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages, especially teaching English language at secondary schools.*

Keywords: *Foreign language, games, innovative technologies, technological tools, methods, techniques.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещается использование современных инновационных технологий в обучении иностранным языкам, особенно в обучении английскому языку в общеобразовательной школе.*

Ключевые слова: *Иностранный язык, игры, инновационные технологии, технологические средства, методы, приемы.*

At present, new reforms on teaching and learning foreign language are being carried out in our country. In particular, the Presidential Decree № 1875 “On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages” on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. New methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages in the country have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). According to CEFR, many new textbooks have been created for pupils of secondary schools and professional education. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process is aimed at improving the quality and effectiveness of education. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language.

We know that the role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking).

Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning and requires the learners to pay attention to the speaker’s pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. There are advantages of using modern technologies in teaching English which make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for pupils:

- Learners can watch and hear videos, presentations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- Learners can listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;
- Use of tape recorders and cassettes to improve listening comprehension.

Today, interactive games are being used much in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help pupils demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the pupil. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful

activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential.

At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the pupil is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and is more comfortable. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Pupils are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the pupil. The pupil is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase learning effectiveness. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach pupils to think independently.

Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of educators in the United States and the United Kingdom:

- “Creative Problem Solving” is the beginning of the story. Pupils are referred to the judgment of the pupils;

- Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to pupils, as they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;

- Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

- “Warm-up exercises” to use various games in the classroom to engage pupils in the lesson;

- Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained or when pupils are tired of writing exercises;

- A chain story method helps to develop pupils’ oral skills;

- Acting characters. This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to pupils;

- “Thinkers meeting” It is possible to “invite” poets and writers such as W. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns. At such times, the use of the wise sayings they utter in the classroom will help young people to become perfect human beings;

- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of pupils and allow all pupils to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops pupils’ logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and correctly. Such methods stimulate the pupil’s desire for knowledge. This makes pupils active participants in the learning process.

REFERENCES

1. O. Hoshimov, I. Yakubov. “METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH” (textbook) Tashkent: Sharq Publishing House, 2003
2. M. Xoldorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. “CHET TILINI O’QITISHDA YORDAMCHI VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH”. Toshkent: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU, 2005.
3. Brown, H.D, 1994 Principles of Language Learning and teaching, Prentice Hall Regents
4. McCoy, R.I 1993. Means to Overcome the Anxieties of Second Language Learners, Foreign Language Annals, pages 185-9, No. 12, 1979.
5. Richards, J.C., 1994 The Language Teaching Matrix, Cambridge University Press.